

Non approximately inner tensor product of C^* -algebras

Rasoul Abazari

Abstract—In this paper, we show that C^* -tensor product of an arbitrary C^* -algebra A , (not unital necessary) and a C^* -algebra B without ground state, have no approximately inner strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms.

Keywords—One-parameter group, C^* -tensor product, Approximately inner, Ground state.

I. INTRODUCTION

Suppose $\{\alpha_t; -\infty < t < \infty\}$ is strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms of a C^* -algebra A , where by strongly continuous we mean $\|\alpha_t(a) - a\| \rightarrow 0$, as $t \rightarrow 0$, for each $a \in A$. We say the group $\{\alpha_t\}$ is approximately inner if there exist a sequence $\{h_n\}$ of hermitian elements of A such that

$$\|e^{ith_n} a e^{ith_n} - \alpha_t(a)\| \rightarrow 0,$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$, for each $a \in A$, where for fixed a the convergence is uniform for t in compact set.

In quantum field theory and statistical mechanics, one of the describes a physical system in the terms of a C^* -algebra A .

In quantum lattice systems the dynamics is given by approximately inner one-parameter groups of $\star$ -automorphism (see the references [5], [6]). It follows that quantum lattice systems have ground state. Recall, has shown the existence of ground state for quantum lattice system in [[4], theorems 2(c) and 4].

If α_t and β_t are strongly continuous one-parameters group of $\star$ -automorphism with infinitesimal quantum δ_1 and δ_2 for C^* -algebras A and B respectively, then $\{\alpha_t \otimes \beta_t\}$ is strongly continuous one-parameter group for $A \otimes B$ with infinitesimal quantum $((\delta_1 \otimes I) + (I \otimes \delta_2))$.

In this paper we shoe that tensor product of an arbitrary C^* -algebras A (not unital necessary) and a C^* -algebras B without ground state, have no approximately inner strongly continues one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms.

Rasoul Abazari is with the Department of Mathematics, Islamic Azad University, Ardabil Branch, Ardabil, IRAN, E-mail: rasoolabazari@gmail.com.

II. PRELIMINARIES

in working with a strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms α_t it is often useful to introduce the unbounded derivation δ which generates the group. suppose α_t is a strongly continuous group of $\star$ -automorphisms of a C^* -algebra A . the generator of the group α_t is a derivation δ given by

$$\delta(a) = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} (\alpha_t(a) - a)/t$$

where the domain $D(\delta)$ of δ is the linear manifolds of all $a \in A$ such that the above limit exists in the sense of norm convergence. It follows from semigroup theory (see [7]) and the fact that α_t are $\star$ -automorphisms that δ has the properties,

- i) $D(\delta)$ is a norm dense linear subset of A and δ is linear mapping of $D(\delta)$ into A .
- ii) $D(\delta)$ is an algebra and if $a, b \in D(\delta)$ then $ab \in D(\delta)$ and $\delta(ab) = \delta(a)b + a\delta(b)$
- iii) $D(\delta)$ is a $\star$ -algebra and if $a \in D(\delta)$ then $a^* \in D(\delta)$ and $\delta(a^*) = \delta(a)^*$
- iv) δ is closed i.e, if $a_n \in D(\delta)$, $\|a_n - a\| \rightarrow 0$ and $\|\delta(a_n) - b\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ then $a \in D(\delta)$ and $\delta(a) = b$.

We present the definitive of a ground state on a C^* -algebra with respect to a one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphism this definitive is essentially the spectral condition of quantum field theory.

Definition 2.1: Suppose $\{\alpha_t\}$ is a one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphism of a C^* -algebra A , we say ω is a ground state of A for the group $\{\alpha_t\}$, if ω is a state of A with the property, if $a, b \in A$ then $\omega(a\alpha_t(b))$ is a continuous function of t and

$$\int h(t)\omega(a\alpha_t(b))dt = 0,$$

for all continuous L^1 -functions h whose Fourier transform

$$\tilde{h}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int e^{-it\lambda} h(t)dt,$$

vanishes on the negative real axis $(-\infty, 0]$.

Theorem 2.1: Suppose $\{\alpha_t\}$ is a one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphism of a C^* -algebra A , suppose δ is the generator of $\{\alpha_t\}$ and D is a core for δ , then a state ω is a ground state for $\{\alpha_t\}$ if and only if

$$-i\omega(a^*\delta(a)) \geq 0$$

for all $a \in D$.

Proof. See [1]

Theorem 2.2: Suppose $\{\alpha_t\}$ is a strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms of a C^* -algebra A , suppose $\{\alpha_t\}$ is approximately inner, then there exists a ground state ω for $\{\alpha_t\}$. This ground state need not be unique.

Proof. See [1]

Let A, B be C^* -algebras and $A \otimes B$ be their algebraic tensor product. Let π_1, π_2 be faithful representation of A, B on Hilbert spaces H_1, H_2 respectively, and define

$$\left\| \sum_j a_j \otimes b_j \right\|_s = \left\| \sum_j \pi_1(a_j) \otimes \pi_2(b_j) \right\|$$

where $a_j \in A, b_j \in B$ and the norm on the right hand side is the operator norm on the Hilbert space $H_1 \oplus H_2$. This norm is the Spatial C^* -norm on $A \otimes B$ and refer to the C^* -algebra $A \otimes_s B$ as the spatial tensor product of A and B .

Let δ_1, δ_2 be generators of strongly continuous one-parameter groups of automorphisms on A, B respectively. We define $\delta_1 \otimes I + I \otimes \delta_2$ on $A \otimes B$ by

$$(\delta_1 \otimes I + I \otimes \delta_2)(a \otimes b) = \delta_1(a) \otimes b + a \otimes \delta_2(b)$$

where $(a \in D(\delta_1), b \in D(\delta_2))$

In this paper we denote $\delta_1 \otimes I + I \otimes \delta_2$ by $\delta_1 \otimes \delta_2$. The $\delta_1 \otimes \delta_2$ is closable $\star$ -derivation and its closure is an infinitesimal generator on $A \otimes_s B$. [1]

Let G be a locally compact group and let μ be a left invariant Haar measure on G and let $L^1(G)$ be the Banach space of all complex valued μ -integrable functions on G . For $f, g \in L^1(G)$ define a multiplication $\star$ and $\star$ -operation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f \star g(x) &= \int_G f(xy)g(y^{-1})dy \\ &= \int_G f(y)g(y^{-1}x)dy, \end{aligned}$$

and $f^*(x)\Delta(x^{-1})\bar{f}(x^{-1})$, where Δ is the modular function on G . Let $f \in L^1(G)$ and define the operator L_f on $L^2(G)$ by $L_f(g) = f \star g, (g \in L^2(G))$, then the mapping $f \rightarrow L_f$ is a bounded representation of the algebra $L^1(G)$. For instance, $4L_{f_1}L_{f_2}(g) = f_1 \star (f_2 \star g) = (f_1 \star f_2) \star g = L_{f_1 \star f_2}(g)$. Hence $L_{f_1 \star f_2} = L_{f_1}L_{f_2}$ the inequality

$$\|f \star g\|_2 \leq \|f\|_1 \|g\|_2,$$

implies that $\|L_f\| \leq \|f\|_1$, where $f \in L^1(G), g \in L^2(G)$.

Suppose $K(G)$ is the set of all complex-valued square summable functions on G with compact support. $K(G)$ is $\star$ -subalgebra of $L^1(G) \cap L^2(G)$. Define

$$T(G) = \{L_f : f \in K(G)\},$$

and $C_r^*(G)$ to be the C^* -algebra generated by $T(G)$. $C_r^*(G)$ is the reduced C^* -algebra of G .

If $f \in L^1(G)$, there exist a sequence $\{f_n\}$ in $K(G)$ such that $\|f_n - f\|_1 \rightarrow 0$ thus

$$\|L_{f_n} - L_f\| \leq \|f_n - f\|_1 \rightarrow 0,$$

therefore $C_r^*(G)$ is the C^* -algebra generated by the set

$$\{L_f : f \in L^1(G)\}.$$

Define $K'(G)$ by

$$K'(G) = \{f \in L^1(G) : f \text{ has a compact support}\}$$

then $K(G) \subseteq K'(G)$ and $\star$ -subalgebra

$$D = \{L_f : f \in K'(G)\}$$

is dense in $C_r^*(G)$

Let θ be a complex-valued measurable function on G , such that θ is bounded on any compact subset of G .

if $f \in K'(G)$, then $\theta f \in K'(G)$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} \int_G |\theta(x)f(x)|dx &= \int_G |\theta(x)||f(x)|dx \\ &\leq \sup_{x \in C} |\theta(x)| \|f\|_1 \end{aligned}$$

where C is the support of f .

Suppose $\text{Hom}(G, R)$ is the set of all real-valued homomorphisms from G to R and θ is a continuous homomorphism in $\text{Hom}(G, R)$.

We define δ_θ from D into D by $\delta_\theta(L_f) = iL_{\theta f}$. Niknam in [] has shown that δ_θ is closable $\star$ -derivation and its closure is an infinitesimal generator of $C_r^*(G)$.

Theorem 2.3: Let G be a locally compact group and $\theta \in \text{Hom}(G, R)$ be measurable function, then δ_θ is closable $\star$ -derivation from D to D and its closure $\bar{\delta}_\theta$ is an infinitesimal generator of a strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms.

Proof. See [1]

In the proof of the above theorem, if we define $\alpha_t : D \rightarrow D$ be $\alpha_t(L_f) = L_{e^{it\theta}f}$, where $f \in K'(G)$, then $\{\alpha_t\}$ is a strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms by infinitesimal generator δ_θ , for $\theta \in \text{Hom}(G, R)$.

III. THE RESULT

In this section, the main result of this work mentioned as a following theorem.

Theorem 3.1: Let A and B be C^* -algebra and B is not unital necessary. Suppose that $\{\alpha_t\}$ and $\{\beta_t\}$ are strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms on A and B with infinitesimal generators δ_1 and δ_2 respectively. If $\{\alpha_t\}$ has not ground state and if there exist an element $x \in B$ such that $\delta_2(x) = 0$,

then, the one-parameter automorphism group $\{\alpha_t \otimes \beta_t\}$ of $A \otimes_s B$ is not approximately inner.

Proof: If $\{\alpha_t \otimes \beta_t\}$ were approximately inner, then, by using Theorem 2.2, would be a ground state ω for $\{\alpha_t \otimes \beta_t\}$ an $A \otimes_s B$. Let Φ be the state on A defined by

$$\Phi(a) = \omega(a \otimes x^*x)$$

where $\delta_2(x) = 0$.

Since

$$\begin{aligned} (a \otimes x)^*(\delta_1 \otimes \delta_2)(a \otimes x) &= (a \otimes x)^*(\delta_1 \otimes I + I \otimes \delta_2)(a \otimes x) \\ &= (a^* \otimes x^*)[(\delta_1 \otimes I)(a \otimes x) + (I \otimes \delta_2)(a \otimes x)] \\ &= (a^* \otimes x^*)[(\delta_1(a) \otimes x) + (a \otimes \delta_2(x))] \\ &= (a^* \otimes x^*)(\delta_1(a) \otimes x) \\ &= (a^* \delta_1(a) \otimes x^*x), \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} -i\Phi(a^*\delta_1(a)) &= -i\omega(a^*\delta_1(a) \otimes x^*x) \\ &= -i\omega((a \otimes x)^*(\delta_1 \otimes \delta_2)(a \otimes x)) \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

it follows by theorem 2.1 that Φ would be a ground state for $\{\alpha_t\}$, the contradiction shows that $\{\alpha_t \otimes \beta_t\}$ is not approximately inner.

Following example clear above theorem:

Example 3.1: If $G = R$ be is a locally compact group, then by Theorem 2.3, there exist a strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms $\{\alpha_t\}$ with infinitesimal generator δ_θ for $\theta \in \text{Hom}(R, R)$ of reduced C^* -algebra $C_r^*(R)$, for function $f \in L^1(R)$, by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & x \in Q \\ 1 & x \in R - Q \end{cases}$$

we have $\delta_\theta(L_f) = 0$, hence if $\{\beta_t\}$ be a one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms on C^* -algebra B without ground state, then by theorem 3.1 $\{\alpha_t \otimes \beta_t\}$ is a strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms on $C_r^*(R) \otimes A$ that is not approximately inner. In particular if G be a discrete group, then by [2], $C_r^*(G)$ has a one parameter group without ground state. Hence, we can apply it instead A in above example.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we had shown that tensor product of an arbitrary C^* -algebra A , (not unital necessary) and a C^* -algebra B without ground state, have no approximately inner strongly continuous one-parameter group of $\star$ -automorphisms.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Dr. A. Niknam for many useful conversations on the subject of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Niknam. A, *Infinitesimal generators of C^* -Algebras*, Potential Analysis, 6 (1997) 1–9.
- [2] Lance.E.C and Niknam. A, *Unbounded derivations of group C^* -Algebras*, Proc. Amer.math.Soc. 61 (2) (1976) 310–314.
- [3] Powers. R.T and Sakai.S, *Existence of ground states and KMS states for approximately inner dynamics*, commun.math.Phys, 39 (1975) 273–288.
- [4] Ruelle. O, commun.math.Phys, 11 (1969) 339–345.
- [5] Robinson. D.W,I: commun.math.Phys, 6 (1967) 151–160. II: commun.math.Phys, 7 (1968) 337–348.
- [6] Ruelle. O, *Statistical mechanics*, New York, W.A. Benjamin, Ins 1969.
- [7] Dunford. N and Schwartz.J.T, *Linear operators*, part I. New York: Interscience pub. 1963.

Rasoul Abazari was born in Ardabil, Iran, in 1982. He received the B.Sc. degree from the University of Pnu, Ardabil, Iran, in 2004, M.Sc. degree from the Tarbiat Moallem University of Tehran, Iran, 2006, and Ph.D in Mathematical Analayaia, Departmet of mathematics, Islamic Azad university, Mashhhd Branch, Iran(2010 present), respectively. From 2007 to 2010 he was a full-time lecturer in university of Islamic Azad university of Ardabil Branch.